

New combinations in *Physotrichia* (Apiaceae)

Rajeev Kumar Singh¹ and Sanjeet Kumar^{2*}

¹Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, AIIMS Road, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

²Biodiversity and Conservation Laboratory, Ambika Prasad Research Foundation, Cuttack, Odisha, India

*E-mail: sanjeetaprf@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9538-397X>

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Abstract: The synonymy of *Spuriodaucus* C.Norman with *Physotrichia* Hiern necessitates two new combinations. The species *Spuriodaucus asper* C.Norman and *S. quarrei* C.Norman are here formally transferred to *Physotrichia*.

Keywords: DR Congo, *Spuriodaucus asper*, *Spuriodaucus quarrei*

Introduction

The African genus *Physotrichia* Hiern contains eight species, namely *P. asper* (C.Norman) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *P. atropurpurea* (C.Norman) Cannon, *P. heracleoides* H.Wolff, *P. longiradiatum* H.Wolff, *P. muriculata* (Welw. ex Hiern) S.Droop & C.C.Towns., *P. quarrei* (C.Norman) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *P. verdickii* C.Norman and *P. welwitschii* Hiern (POWO, 2025). The genus is distributed across Angola, Burundi, DR Congo, Malawi, Tanzania and Zambia (POWO, 2025). All species except *P. welwitschii* are recorded from DR Congo, where *P. asper*, *P. quarrei* and *P. verdickii* are considered endemic. The genus *Spuriodaucus* C.Norman is currently treated as a synonym of *Physotrichia* (Kubitzki, 2018; Clarkson, 2021). Accordingly, the two species *Spuriodaucus asper* C.Norman and *S. quarrei* C.Norman are here formally transferred to *Physotrichia*.

New combinations

Physotrichia asper (C.Norman) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Spuriodaucus asper* C.Norman, J. Bot. 70: 137. 1932.

Figure 1: Holotype of *Spuriodaucus asper* C. Norman (BM000902734, © The Natural History Museum, London)

Figure 2: Isotype of *Spuriodaucus asper* C. Norman (K000310824, © The Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew)

Figure 3: Holotype of *Spuriodaucus quarrei* C. Norman (BM000902733, © The Natural History Museum, London)

Figure 4: Isotype of *Spuriodaucus quarrei* C. Norman (BR0000008969026, © Herbarium of National Botanic Garden of Belgium)

Holotype: DR Congo, Mount Kundelungu, 14 May 1908, *T. Kässner 2158* (BM000902734!, Figure 1); isotypes K000310824! (Figure 2), P00462029!, P00462030!, P00462031!.

Distribution: Endemic to DR Congo (Democratic Republic of the Congo).

Physotrichia quarrei (C.Norman) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Spuriodaucus quarrei* C.Norman, Contr. Fl. Katanga Suppl. 3: 120. 1930.

Holotype: DR Congo, Kafubu, 5 April 1927, *P. Quarré 255* (BM000902733!, Figure 3); isotypes BR0000008968012!, BR0000008969026! (Figure 4), BR0000008968692!.

Distribution: Endemic to DR Congo.

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